

ISic3814

I.Sicily inscription 3814

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact provenance unknown; seen by Libertini (1921) in villa Di Mauro,
contr. Diana

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 900

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀρτεμιδώρας

Apparatus

Meligunìs Lipára XII

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

PHI 334221

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 119

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 225 no.48
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